

Adsorption mechanisms of small aromatic compounds in cross-linked dextran gel

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ABSTRACT

A series of 12 small aromatic compounds, along with glucose and cellobiose, was selected to analyze how structural and physicochemical properties influence the adsorption of small aromatic compounds onto cross-linked dextran resin (Sephadex® G-25) in aqueous chromatography. This group of compounds contain structural features that are common in phytochemicals, such as methoxy, hydroxyl and hydroxymethyl groups and glucosides. Retention factors of these compounds were measured in similar conditions at different temperatures and compared with their structural and physicochemical information. Enthalpy-entropy compensation plot distinguished groups of compounds that are expected to have differing adsorption mechanisms. Retention factors at 21°C varied for the aromatic compounds from 1.27, for benzyl β-D-glucopyranose, to 2.48 for 3-methoxyphenol. Temperature increase from 21°C to 50°C had a mild effect on the strength of π-interaction mediated adsorption. However, it diminished hydrogen bonding related adsorption effects in the aromatic compounds. An explanation of the variations in the adsorption strength is proposed based on the structure effects of the compounds. Inductive- and resonance effects affecting π-interaction are considered together with hydrogen bonding and steric effects. An incremental adsorptivity model is used to demonstrate how the observed retention factors originate from these structure effects, and how they account for the differences with the measured retention factors in different temperatures.

1. Introduction

The goal of this study is to explain the solute related physicochemical and structural factors affecting the adsorption strength of small aromatic compounds in aqueous chromatography with epichlorohydrin cross-linked dextran gel. When these factors are well understood, it is possible to pre-determine the usefulness and separation efficiency of this type of chromatography for the separation of a large variation of phytochemicals.

Cross-linked dextran separation materials have been widely used in chromatography since their discovery in the 1950's [1]. One particularly interesting property is that epichlorohydrin cross-linked dextran gels adsorb hydrophobic substances, even though the gel itself is hydrophilic. This property is useful in the separation of aromatic compounds. In addition, this property allows the use of water as solvent, even though the target chemicals can be only moderately water-soluble. The exact adsorption mechanism is not known, but it is expected to be associated with the glyceryl ether linkages. Sephadex® G-25, in particular, is used for the separation of phenolic compounds from biomaterial

[2–4], flavonoids [5] and phytochemicals found in wood bark [6].

In earlier studies, detailed structural and physicochemical information has not been linked to adsorption strength differences, or to the impact of temperature [7–13]. Also, the thermodynamic quantities of adsorption equilibrium have not been determined in similar system. Furthermore, the enthalpy-entropy compensation plot, presented in this text, allows the comparison of possible differences in the adsorption mechanisms of the compounds. As a result, a detailed and comprehensive understanding of the adsorption related factors has been achieved. This information was used to create an incremental prediction model to demonstrate the structural effects behind relative differences in adsorptivity of small aromatic compounds.

A representative image of the study system with cross-linked dextran gel is presented in Fig. 1. Dextran backbone consists mostly of α-O-(1-6)-straight chain glucosides, with a smaller number of α-O-(1-3)-glucosidic branching. Dextran cross-linking is based on α-O-(1-3)-glyceryl ethers. However, some partly reacted 1-O-(α-D-glucosyl)glycerols may remain from the epichlorohydrin cross-linking reactions.

As will be shown in the review of previous research on this topic in

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Section 2, the relationships between molecular properties of solutes and their retention in Sephadex type gels is still far from resolved. This is true especially for certain phytochemicals found in wood bark, for which Sephadex G-10 has shown a significant separation factor [6]. Current information of the adsorption mechanism of aromatic compounds via π -interaction and hydrogen bonding is limited. Also, the adsorption site is an open question, even though it is considered to be associated with glyceryl ether linkages. The impact of temperature has also not been studied thoroughly.

To study the adsorption, retention data was measured for 14 compounds. These include small aromatic compounds (anisole **1**, benzene **2**, acetophenone **3**), difunctional compounds containing hydroxyl groups (methoxyphenols **4-6** and hydroxybenzyl alcohols, **7-10**), glucosylated aromatic compounds; (benzyl β -D-glucopyranoside **11** and salicin **12**), and also free sugars (glucose **13**, and cellobiose **14**). The pulse method and the frontal analysis method were used under isocratic conditions.

Frontal analysis provided supportive information on the linear adsorption properties within the studied system and the pulse method gave comparable retention factors of the compounds. The experimental observations are explained by retention factor differences based on structural and physicochemical properties, including activity coefficients in infinite dilution. The impact of temperature is also explained.

As there has been a lot of previous work conducted with relevant findings and preliminary hypotheses for the nature of adsorption with Sephadex® gel, we have included **section 2**. Review of Previous Research. This is followed by 3. Materials and Methods and 4. Results and Discussion sections.

2. Review of previous research

Cross-linked dextran gel, and its use in column chromatography of water-soluble substances, was introduced in 1959 [1]. This type of gel is composed of dextran that is cross-linked with epichlorohydrin under alkaline conditions [1]. Usually, dextran refers to exopolysaccharide synthesized by lactic acid bacteria or their enzymes in the presence of sucrose. Dextran is composed of a linear backbone of D-glucopyranosyl units linked by α -(1,6) linkages, with occasional branches formed through α -(1,4), α -(1,3), or α -(1,2) linkages [9,14–15]. G-value indicates the water regain of the gel multiplied by 10. Therefore, a smaller value indicates a higher degree of cross-linking by glyceryl ether linkages [16–18]. In size exclusion chromatography, fractionation range of Sephadex® G-25 for globular proteins is Mr 1000-5000 and for dextrans Mp 100-5000 [17].

The extent of cross-link density affects retention of aromatic compounds in Sephadex materials. Phenol adsorbs more strongly to tightly cross-linked gels in the order G-10, G-15 and G-25 [9]. Even though aromatic substances are sometimes retained during liquid chromatography on various sorbents such as charcoal, cellulose, silica, aluminum

oxide, and polyacrylamide, these effects are much less pronounced than in the case of Sephadex® dextran gels [9].

Further insight into the structure and possible adsorption mechanisms can be obtained with low temperature X-ray diffraction and calorimetry studies [19–21]. Sephadex® G-15 studies at -100° to 25°C show that the hydrogen-bonded structure of water in the proximity of the gel, is largely distorted due to hydrogen bonding with the surface hydroxyl groups. In addition, bulk-like water is present in the central region of G-15 pores to an appreciable amount. As a conclusion this water can be involved in the hydration processes of solutes rather than forming hydrogen bonds with the gel, and thus it can play a role in the separation processes of solutes [22].

Low temperature studies with Sephadex® G-25 show that the non-crystallizing water, corresponding to the hydration water, accounts for 18% of the total water within the gel. It remains partially unfrozen during cooling and undergoes ice crystallization during rewarming. There appears to be two different glass transition states during heating in different temperature ranges. This may be an indication of two water assemblies in two different and (partly) separated compartments in the gel material. These could be either compartmentalized by the network structure made of cross-linked dextran and/or confined within the narrow spaces formed by the entangled dextran chains [21]. Results from aqueous Sephadex® G-10 and G-25 chromatography indicate that distribution factors differing from unity with small non-aromatic solute molecules like *t*-butanol, can be explained by the anomalous properties of vicinal water layers at the gel matrix-water interface. Solute molecules may have a bulk/water/vicinal water distribution coefficient differing significantly from unity [23].

Sephadex® G-25 was originally developed for size exclusion chromatography with sieving property [1]. However, the observed adsorption of small aromatic molecules is based on a different mechanism [24]. Sephadex® G-25 separates especially small aromatic and heterocyclic substances, which have a greater tendency to be adsorbed than aliphatic substances. Basic groups in a molecule increase, and acid groups decrease, the adsorption. This can be seen e.g. with differences in K_D values of mono-substituted benzoic acid derivatives [7]. Groups that increase adsorption are reported to do this in the order expected from their electron donating properties. On the other hand, nitro- and carboxylic acid groups decrease adsorption. Both the number- and position of hydroxyl groups, and the effect of other substituent groups, effect the strength of adsorption. With some molecules, it is considered that steric factors may govern their penetration to gel grains [8]. It is also possible that internal hydrogen bonding of the solutes can impact adsorption [7].

Several specific adsorptivity findings have been reported. When comparing the adsorption of benzene, toluene, phenol and anisole on Sephadex® G-15, the electron-donating substituents increase the adsorption of the substituted benzenes more than they do for substituted phenols [12]. Methylation in vanillin and syringic acid results in adsorption behavior very much like a mono-hydroxylic acid. Two

Fig. 1. Representative image of Sephadex® gel and 3-methoxyphenol (blue). Chlorohydrin induced cross-linking is shown with cyan color. Extension of the system can occur with α -1-6 glucosidic linkages (R and R') and α -1-3-glyceryl ether dextran cross-linking (R and R'').

vicinal hydroxyl groups in caffeic acid induce strong adsorption properties, and this effect is reduced by methylating one or both of the hydroxyl groups. 2,4-dihydroxy benzoic acid is less strongly adsorbed than the 2,3-substituted one, but this difference disappears in electrolyte solution. Dihydroxylated naphthalenes are much stronger adsorbed than hydroxylated phenols. However, dihydroxydiphenols are only slightly more adsorbed than di- and triphenols [2]. Flavonols are generally adsorbed more strongly than flavanones [10]. Some flavonoids and tannins are so strongly adsorbed to Sephadex® G-25 that they are not eluted when pure water is used as the eluent [25]. Scarcely water-soluble free iso-flavones cannot be eluted with water, but they can be liberated from the column with ammonium hydroxide solution [26].

Special binding forces between solutes with π -electrons and the glyceryl ethers in Sephadex® matrix are seen as one possible source of adsorption. This is linked with stronger adsorption with more cross-linked gels [9]. The rate of elution depends also on the number, and orientation of the free hydroxyl groups, i.e. those not involved in internal hydrogen bonding, and the extent to which these groups are accessible [2]. There have been attempts to bind the strength of adsorptivity to Hamilton equation [27–29] and to create a group contribution method to predict adsorption differences within a group of aromatic compounds [30]. These attempts have not provided a detailed understanding of the factors affecting the adsorption equilibrium.

For non-aromatic alcohols, hydrophobic interaction has been shown to be the major determinant of affinity. Adsorption increases with increasing carbon chain length, while the presence of a hydroxyl group or groups reduces affinity. Adsorption is likely affected by van der Waals-London dispersion forces which increase with increasing bulk of the non-polar moiety of the molecules. As a result, adsorption differences can show a linear Gibbs free energy relation [13]. Aliphatic sorption mechanism, e.g. when increasing the carbon chain length, increases adsorption with moderately hydrophilic and small compounds with Sephadex® gels [13,31]. Similar types of results are observed with surfactants with an aromatic or steroidal head group and a long alkyl chain, and with oligoethylene glycol decyl ethers. However, strong surfactants have weak adsorptivity and it decreases with increasing critical micelle concentration. It is likely that the retention of micelles is based pre-dominantly on molecular sieving mechanism [31].

With lignin depolymerization products, the efficiency of size exclusion separation using Sephadex® G-10 column chromatography decreases for aromatic monomers. This is likely due to aromatic rings and phenolic hydroxyl groups in the monomers which decrease the effective size exclusion. This effect can be mitigated by using alkaline mobile phase which induces electrostatic repulsion between negatively charged aromatic monomers and the Sephadex® G-10 gel [32].

Some similar findings and conclusions highlighting the π -interaction and hydrogen bonding as the key factors in the adsorption mechanism are observed with Sephadex® LH-20 when aromatic compounds are eluted using methanol and isopropanol as solvents. Also, studies with simple aromatic compounds on activated carbon materials show that the extension and density of π -electrons and steric complexity affect adsorption. These properties have been used as factors in incremental adsorption models [33].

In association with the structure and functionalities of the solutes and the influence of water, physicochemical properties play a role in retention behavior. In principle, a higher octanol-water partition coefficient (Log P) indicates stronger adsorption when hydrophobic interaction takes place during adsorption [34,35]. Similar effect can also be seen in solutes' activity coefficients in infinite dilution in water. This information can be used to predict the elution order of polar versus non-polar compounds in chromatography [36]. However, this type of information has not yet been closely examined with aromatic compounds and cross-linked dextran material.

Temperature impacts adsorption on cross-linked dextran materials. Phenol, and hydroxybenzoates and halogenated phenols exhibit negative enthalpy changes, whereas small alcohols (MeOH, *n*-BuOH, and *n*-

petanol) and glucose have positive enthalpy changes. Entropy changes can also be either positive (phenol, small alcohols, glucose, *p*-F-, *p*-Cl- and *p*-Br-phenols) or negative (hydroxybenzoates and *p*-I-phenol). The changes are also seen in adsorption, which either gets stronger in lower temperatures (hydroxylated and halogenated compounds), or is not strongly affected, or can even be negatively affected, like with *p*-tert-butylphenol [20,36]. It is possible to consider that ΔH represents the strength of the interaction in between phenols and Sephadex® gel. Interestingly, the adsorption of sterically hindered *p*-tert-butylphenol is not strongly impacted by temperature. However, it has a strong adsorption to Sephadex®. Its ΔH is close to zero and its ΔS is small and positive [37].

Studies focused on purines indicate that the adsorption to Sephadex® G-10 shows correlations with π -electron delocalization energy, electron donating ability, electron accepting ability, basic and acidic *pKa* and water solubility. However, experimental results indicate that purines interact primarily with the dextran portion of the Sephadex®. This is in contrast to substituted benzene derivatives, which are considered to interact primarily with the glyceryl ether cross-linkages of Sephadex® [11].

There are strong indications that adsorption mechanisms of the aromatic compounds, and its relative strength, are linked with π -interaction and hydrogen bonding. Structural features, especially the substitution pattern of the benzene ring, and steric constraints, impact the strength of adsorption. It is evident that the electronic nature of the substituents plays a role in adsorption. The strength of adsorption is expected to be affected also by physicochemical properties, like octanol-water partition coefficient, and temperature. Adsorption sites are in high likelihood at the glycidyl ether cross linkages in the cross-linked dextran. All in all, there are various properties that are known to affect adsorption, but often the historic information is not sufficient to predict the retention order, and the strength of adsorption. This study aims to provide a comprehensive explanation on the factors that affect the adsorption strength of small aromatic compounds and a model that demonstrates how all these properties act together.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Selection of compounds

Selection of compounds for the test series was based on structural features that occur frequently in phytochemicals. It was reported earlier that the elution pattern of triandrin, salicin and picein did not follow the same elution order with Sephadex® G-10 as with resin CA10GC in Na⁺ form [6]. More precisely, it was shown that triandrin elutes later than salicin and picein with Sephadex® G-10. These glucosylated compounds resemble each other structurally and are of similar size. This suggests that other factors than hydrophilicity or molecular size are also of importance [6]. Therefore it was considered important to include only minor differences between the studied molecules to observe the impact of structure on adsorption.

The number of possible structures of small molecules increases with every new structural variation, e.g. a benzene ring can have 10 distinct substitution patterns if three different substituents are used. Therefore, to limit the size of the test series, the choice of substituents was limited to those that are often encountered in phytochemicals and that allow the comparison of adsorption properties based on the *o*-, *m*-, and *p*-pattern. Compounds were also selected from within the same molecular weight range to allow for comparison of physicochemical properties. In addition, there is a scarcity of commercially available glycosylated aromatic compounds available, which limit the options for glycosylated model compounds.

Aniline, benzene, phenol and acetophenone (compounds 1–4) were selected as well-known reference compounds. The test series was extended with phenolic compounds containing either a methoxy substituent (compounds 5–7) or a hydroxymethyl substituent (compounds

8-10) and finally also with two glucosylated compounds: benzyl β -D-glucopyranoside and salicin (compounds 11-12). Glucose and cellobiose were included as well (compounds 13-14), to allow for comparison with free sugars.

The solutes that were used in selected for this study are shown in Fig. 2.

3.2. Materials

Sephadex® G-25, anisole 99%, benzene anhydrous 99.8%, acetophenone 99+%, 2-methoxyphenol 99+%, 3-methoxyphenol 96 %, 4-methoxyphenol 99 %, 3-hydroxybenzyl alcohol 99+%, 4-hydroxybenzyl alcohol 99% and D-glucopyranoside $\geq 99.5\%$ (GC) and Blue Dextran were obtained from Sigma Aldrich. Benzyl β -D-glucopyranoside min. 97 % was obtained from Synthos. D-(+)-cellobiose 98+%, D(-)-salicin 99+% and 2-hydroxybenzyl alcohol 99% were obtained from Thermo Scientific.

All chemical reagents were used without further purification. Sample solutions were degassed by sonification before experiments. All experiments and solutions were made with ultrapure water that was produced by using Evoqua laboratory water system including UV filtering and deionization.

3.3. Chromatographic set-up

The chromatography unit consisted of two Knauer P 4.1S HPLC-pumps (KNAUER Wissenschaftliche Geräte GmbH, Berlin, Germany) and a two-channel Knauer degasser for the feed and eluent solutions. The column outlet stream was monitored by using a refractive index detector (RI 2000, Schambeck SFD GmbH, Bad Honnef, Germany), and with ultraviolet (UV) absorbance detector (Waters 2487, Waters Corporation, Milford, Massachusetts, U.S.). UV wavelength detection in the experiments was varied in between 200 and 280 nm depending on the adsorbance properties of the solutes. The system control and data collection were performed using an in-house LabView program

(National Instruments) [38].

Chromatographic experiments were carried out using a top-down flow. The main characteristics of the separation materials and conditions that were used in this study are shown in Table 1.

The porosity of the packed bed was determined with a Blue Dextran void volume method with detection at 620 nm.

Temperature controlled measurements were performed using water circulation around the column from Julabo® 200F water bath, Julabo GmbH, Seelbach (Schutter), Baden-Württemberg, Germany. Pulse runs for compounds, and the frontal analysis for compound 7, were performed at room temperature 21°C (20 + 3°C), 35°C and 50°C. The thermodynamic calculations at the lowest temperature were based on temperature 21°C, except for compound 4, which was calculated at 23°C.

3.4. Staircase frontal analysis (FA)

Staircase frontal analysis was used to measure adsorption isotherms, based on Eq. (1) [39].

$$q_i^{Feed}(\bar{c}^{Feed}) = q_i^{Init}(\bar{c}^{Init}) + \frac{(t_{R,i}^* - (L/u)) * (c_i^{Feed} - c_i^{Init})}{F * (L/u)} \quad (1)$$

Table 1

Separation material's properties and column dimensions in the experiments.

Separation material	Sephadex® G-25
Matrix	cross-linked dextran
particle size, μm	20-80 μm > 80 %
Bed porosity	0.41
Diameter of bed	15 mm
Height of bed	67.7-71.3 cm
bed volume	119.6-125.9 mL
extra column volume	2.04 mL

Fig. 2. Compounds selected for the test series.

Loadings q_i^{feed} are in equilibrium with the feed concentrations, \bar{c}^{feed} . q_i^{init} is the initial loading, ε the column porosity, L is the column length and u the linear velocity. The dead-time t_0 was calculated as $t_0 = L/u$. F is the phase ratio, $F = (1 - \varepsilon)/\varepsilon$, where ε is the porosity of the bed [39].

Based on this, the differences in loading were calculated with Eq. (2).

$$\Delta q = \frac{\Delta c * (u - u_s)}{F * u_s} \quad (2)$$

Δq is the difference in loading in relation to Δc , which represents the difference in initial concentration in staircase platform. u is the velocity of the liquid and u_s is the velocity of the solute.

Staircase frontal analysis was performed for 2-methoxyphenol (compound **7**) at room temperature (21°C) in 4 concentration steps and at 50°C, at three concentration levels.

Assuming that the adsorption behavior of the compounds in the selected concentration range is linear, loading q can be defined with Henry's constant a , which is the slope of q/c , Eq. (3).

$$q = ac \quad (3)$$

3.5. Pulse experiments

In pulse experiments, sample concentrations were 10 mM aq, the column loading (VF) was 2% of the bed volume (BV), and the flowrate (q) was 0.5 BV/h. Feed volume and the flow rate were adjusted accordingly.

Pulse runs were performed for all compounds in the test series in room temperature (21°C) and at 50°C, and for 4 selected compounds also at 35°C.

Retention times t_R were calculated based on the first moment μ_1 of the UV signal. The RI signal was used for glucose and cellobiose after smoothing with Savitzky-Golay filtering [40] in MatLab v9.13.0 [41].

For pulse experiments, the retention factor k was calculated with Eq. (4).

$$k = (t_R - t_0)/t_0 \quad (4)$$

t_R is the retention time of the measured compound, and t_0 is the elution time of an unretained compound [42]. With linear adsorption terms, distribution constant is independent of sample component concentration. k is used to quantify affinity [43,44] and it represents physically the ratio of the weight of the solute in the stationary phase to that in the mobile phase [45].

3.6. Activity coefficients at infinite dilution in water

Activities at infinite dilution in water, γ_∞ , were calculated with the nonrandom two-liquid model [46] with Redlich-Kwong equation-of-state (NRTL-RK) in Aspen Plus V.14. software [47]. The analysis tool was employed to perform the property estimation for a mixture of each molecule with water. Molecules were added to the simulator as conventional components.

The activity coefficient of anisole **1** was calculated with UNIFAC-model, because the NRTL-RK model in Aspen Plus V.14 software did not include interaction parameters for the anisole-water pair and could not predict the non-ideal behavior of the mixture. γ_∞ was not calculated for benzyl β -D-glucopyranoside **11**, as it is not included in the Aspen Plus database. The results obtained with conditions 10 mM, 22°C and 15 bar were selected for further analysis in this study.

3.7. Van't Hoff plot, enthalpy, entropy and Gibbs free energy

Change in Gibbs free energy ΔG° consists of enthalpy ΔH° and entropy ΔS° as shown below in Eq. (5).

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (5)$$

This relation can also be described by using K , a dimensionless

thermodynamic equilibrium constant of adsorption, as shown in Eq. (6).

$$\Delta G^\circ = -RT\ln(K) \quad (6)$$

In here, R is universal gas constant (8.314 J K⁻¹mol⁻¹), T temperature and K is the thermodynamic equilibrium constant of adsorption. K indicates the ratio of concentration of the solute in the stationary and mobile phase. phase ratio F can be calculated based on the porosity of the gel ε , see Eq. (7):

$$F = \frac{V_s}{V_m} = \frac{\varepsilon}{1 - \varepsilon} \quad (7)$$

With linear isotherms, K is directly proportional to the retention factor k and the phase ratio F , see Eq. (8):

$$K = F * k \quad (8)$$

k value was determined from the retention time information from the pulse runs for all compounds in different temperatures.

Temperature-related changes in the system can be described with linear van't Hoff equation Eq. (9) [48]

$$\ln(K) = \ln(k * F) = -\left(\frac{-\Delta H^\circ}{R}\right) * \frac{1}{T} + \frac{-\Delta S^\circ}{R} \quad (9)$$

Equilibria change is related to changes in both entropy and enthalpy, and they correspond to the slope of the Van't Hoff graph with $\ln(K)$ (y-axis) and $1/T$ (x-axis).

Therefore, the slope in the plot represents $\frac{-\Delta H^\circ}{R}$ and the intercept $\frac{\Delta S^\circ}{R}$. Van't Hof plot was used to derive ΔH° and ΔS° values, which were used to derive ΔG° with Eq. (5) at standard conditions T=20°C.

Retention factors at different temperatures (1 and 2) are related to Gibbs free energy as shown in Eq. (10).

$$\Delta G_B - \Delta G_A = -RT\ln\left(\frac{k_2}{k_1}\right) \quad (10)$$

3.8. Physicochemical parameters and structural descriptors

Information for this study was collected as follows: Log P predictions from XLogP3 [49], water solubility predictions from WSKOWWIN v.1.42 [50], molar volume, surface tension, and polarizability from the ACD/ChemScetch predictor [51]. Topological polar surface areas were self-calculated based on the structures [52].

3.9. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient

Spearman's rank correlation coefficients (r) [53,54] and associated p -values were calculated by using functions in SciPy library [55]. This statistical approach provided information on the monotonic relationships between k and the physicochemical properties of the compounds, as well as in between experimental k values and those k values predicted based on the sums of structural effects.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Linearity as adsorption behavior

Staircase frontal analysis (FA) was performed to verify that the adsorption behavior of the compounds is linear. FA was performed with 2-methoxyphenol **7** at room temperature (21°C) and at 50°C. **7** was selected to study the linear adsorptivity, as it belongs to the group of methoxyphenols. This group has the highest k' values in the studied series, and **7** has a high water solubility that allows the required high concentrations in the FA experiments.

FA results in rt and 50°C are presented in Fig. 3.

Henry's constants were determined according to Eq. (3), resulting $a=1.44$ at room temperature (21°C) and $a=1.32$ at 50°C.

Fig. 3. Measured staircase frontal analysis plots in room temperature (21°C) and 50°C and the corresponding linear isotherms for 2-methoxyphenol 7 with plot intercept at 0. Results based on loading q are shown in the plot on right.

Based on the results from the staircase frontal analysis, we expect that the substances in the test series behave linearly. There may be additional factors causing nonlinearity in isotherms at higher concentrations above 85 mmol/L. However, the further analyses are based on pulse runs at a concentration level 10 mM, which is so low that linear adsorption due to Henry's region can be expected.

4.2. Pulse runs

Pulse run experiments were performed to determine retention factors k to compare the adsorptivity of the compounds in similar conditions. Higher k value from the pulse runs of similar compounds indicate stronger adsorption, and/or stronger preference of the adsorbent phase when compared with the aqueous phase, thus resulting in longer retention times. We used k values in this study for relative comparisons of the adsorption behavior rather than as an absolute measure of affinity.

Pulse runs were performed for all compounds at room temperature (21°C, except 23°C for compound 4) and at 50°C. In addition, acetophenone (compound 3) and 4-, 3 and 2-methoxyphenols (compounds 5, 6 and 7) were measured at 35°C. Results are presented graphically in Fig. 4 and numerically in Table 2.

4.2.1. Accuracy and precision of the pulse runs

Reliability of the results was confirmed with a series of 4 runs in similar test conditions for compound 6 in rt and 3 runs for compound 6 at 50°C. Retention values had a variation of 0.30 % at rt and 0.33% at 50°C. The number of theoretical plates, which measures the column

Fig. 4. Retention factors k in room temperature (black circles), 35°C (blue diamonds) and 50°C (black bars). Values are presented in y-axis and the compound numbers in x-axis.

efficiency, varied between 380 and 1065, with average value of 563. This indicated that mass transfer resistance was not significant, and the retention time measurements are adequate for this study.

4.3. Impact of physicochemical parameters on adsorptivity

4.3.1. Spearman's rank correlation coefficient

Spearman's rank correlation analysis was used to identify those physicochemical parameters of the compounds in the test series that show similarity with their ranking order with adsorption strength. Correlations were calculated for the properties all compounds (1–14), or the aromatic subset (1–12), and k values at 21°C and 50°C. A Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (r) with an absolute value greater than 0.60 ($|r| > 0.60$) was considered to indicate a meaningful correlation. Results with p -values < 0.01 were deemed statistically significant. Calculated r and p -values for the physicochemical properties listed in Table 2, in relation to k at 21°C and 50°C, are shown in Table 3. The results on the left include all compounds (1–14), while those on the right consider only the aromatic compounds (1–12). Bold font indicates values with $r > |\pm 0.60|$.

These results show different r values at 21°C and 50°C. Statistically significant monotonic relationships were observed with Log P, σ , TPSA, and HBD. Aromatic compounds 1–12 gave different results when compared with the full test series 1–14. These property relationships, at 21°C and 50°C, are illustrated in Fig. 5.

When considering Spearman's rank correlation for Log γ_{∞} , it is noteworthy that compound 11 was excluded from the analysis due to missing Log γ_{∞} data. In addition, compounds 5–7 and 8–10 exhibited similar predicted Log γ_{∞} values, meaning that substitution pattern differences within these groups are not captured in the ranking. Nevertheless, it is likely that aromatic compounds have a significant monotonic relationship in between k and Log γ_{∞} .

These results suggest that a higher Log P value is generally associated with stronger adsorption. In contrast, higher values of surface tension, polar surface area, and the number of hydrogen bond donors tend to correlate with weaker adsorption. Interestingly, the Log γ_{∞} values of the aromatic compounds 1–12 exhibited a strong similarity in ranking with k , as indicated by Spearman's rank correlation. Lower γ_{∞} values tend to correspond to stronger adsorption.

4.3.2. Octanol water partition coefficient

To obtain comparable values of Log P, it was decided to use the same prediction method for all compounds. Log P prediction programs have been employed to estimate this property for druglike molecules with standard errors 0.3–0.4 log units in favorable cases [56]. Using KOWWIN [57] and XlogP3 [49], deviations of approximately 0.4 log units from experimental values can be expected [58]. For this study, we compared predictions from KOWWIN v.1.68, XlogP3 and the ACD/ChemSketch

Table 2Table contains retention factors *k* from the pulse runs, physicochemical properties and molecular descriptors of the compounds, and the associated enthalpy, entropy and Gibbs free energy change.

n:	Name	CAS	<i>k</i> 21°C	<i>k</i> 35°C	<i>k</i> 50°C	Mw	V _m (cm ³ / mol)	Log P	Log S (mol/ L)	H- bond donors	H- bond acceptors	σ dyne/ cm	α 10 E-24 cm ³	TPSA Å ²	Log γ _{oo}	ΔH (kJ/ mol)	ΔS (J/K mol)	ΔG (kJ/ mol)	
o			<i>Note 1</i>			<i>Note 2</i>		<i>Note 3</i>	<i>Note 4</i>			<i>Note 5</i>		<i>Note 6</i>	<i>Note 7</i>	<i>Note 8</i>			<i>Note 9</i>
1	anisole	100-66-3	1.99		1.95	108.14	113.40	2.1	-1.8	0	1	29.30	13.05	9	3.06*	-0.51	0.96	-0.79	
2	benzene	71-43-2	1.75		1.76	78.11	89.40	2.1	-1.6	0	0	28.80	10.40	0	3.39	0.14	2.11	-0.48	
3	acetophenone	98-86-2	1.92	1.89	1.86	120.15	120.90	1.9	-1.4	0	1	34.10	14.38	17	3.17	-0.82	-0.39	-0.70	
4	phenol	108-95-2	2.09		2.01	94.11	87.80	1.5	-0.6	1	1	40.90	11.15	20	1.05	-1.14	-0.78	-0.92	
5	4-methoxyphenol	150-76-5	2.29	2.17	2.06	124.14	111.80	1.6	-0.9	1	2	38.60	13.80	30	1.13	-2.80	-5.66	-1.14	
6	3-methoxyphenol	150-19-6	2.48	2.33	2.20	124.14	111.80	1.3	-0.7	1	2	38.60	13.80	30	1.13	-3.34	-6.84	-1.34	
7	2-methoxyphenol	90-05-1	2.17	2.09	2.00	124.14	111.80	1.3	-1.2	1	2	38.60	13.80	30	1.13	-2.22	-4.11	-1.01	
8	2-hydroxybenzyl alcohol	90-01-7	1.99		1.86	124.14	101.60	0.7	0.4	2	2	54.10	13.71	41	1.38	-1.82	-3.51	-0.79	
9	3-hydroxybenzyl alcohol	620-24-6	1.97		1.85	124.14	101.60	0.5	0.6	2	2	54.10	13.71	41	1.38	-1.79	-3.46	-0.78	
10	4-hydroxybenzyl alcohol	623-05-2	1.93		1.81	124.14	101.60	0.3	0.8	2	2	54.10	13.71	41	1.38	-1.74	-3.46	-0.72	
11	benzyl β-D- glucopyranoside	4304-12- 5	1.27		1.29	270.28	191.70	-0.7	-0.6	4	6	69.20	26.41	99		0.40	0.32	0.30	
12	salicin	138-52-3	1.31		1.30	286.27	204.90	-1.2	-0.2	5	7	77.60	28.85	120	1.45	-0.08	-1.08	0.23	
13	glucose	50-99-7	1.05		1.07	180.16	104.00	-3.2	0.7	5	6	81.70	14.77	110	-0.29	0.32	-1.51	0.76	
14	cellobiose	528-50-7	0.94		0.94	342.30	193.60	-3.6	0.5	8	11	110.80	28.06	190	-1.15	0.26	-2.70	1.05	

Note 1: Temperature in between 20 ± 3°C, *Note 2:* ACD/ChemSctch predictor (ACD) with standard deviation (sd) ± 5 cm³/mol, *Note 3:* XLogP3, *Note 4:* WSKOWWIN v.1.42, *Note 5:* ACD with sd ±5.0 dyne/cm, *Note 6:* ACD, sd ±5.0 10E-24 cm³, *Note 7:* Calculated based on structure [52] *Note 8:* Predicted in Aspen Plus V.14. at 10 mM, 22°C and 15 bar, with NRTL-RK model in Aspen Plus V.14, * anisole γ_{oo} was predicted with UNIFAC-model in Aspen+, value for compound 11 was not obtained due to missing interaction parameters for the model, *Note 9:* Gibbs free energy change was calculated at normal temperature 20°C and pressure 1 atmosphere.

Table 3
Calculated r and p -values for the physicochemical properties listed in Table 2.

Property	1-14	1-14	1-14	1-14	aromatic	Aromatic	Aromatic	Aromatic
	r 21 °C	r 50 °C	p -value, 21 °C	p -value, 50 °C	1-12 r 21 °C	1-12 r 50 °C	1-12 p -value, 21 °C	1-12 p -value, 50 °C
w	-0.50	-0.58	0.067	0.031	-0.21	-0.33	0.507	0.291
Log P	0.59	0.68	0.026	0.008	0.35	0.49	0.265	0.106
Log S	-0.38	-0.48	0.180	0.081	-0.15	-0.29	0.649	0.366
V_m	-0.33	-0.27	0.242	0.345	-0.30	-0.21	0.347	0.507
σ	-0.60	-0.67	0.023	0.008	-0.36	-0.48	0.248	0.118
Polarizability ¹	-0.49	-0.45	0.072	0.102	-0.23	-0.17	0.464	0.597
TPSA	-0.57	-0.65	0.035	0.011	-0.32	-0.46	0.312	0.131
HBD ²	-0.59	-0.69	0.025	0.006	-0.35	-0.51	0.259	0.093
HBA ³	-0.49	-0.57	0.078	0.034	-0.18	-0.31	0.582	0.323
Log γ_∞ ⁴	-0.08	-0.02	0.800	0.942	-0.79	-0.69	0.004	0.018

¹ Values derived using ACD/ChemScetch predictor

² hydrogen bond donors

³ hydrogen bond acceptors

⁴ Log γ_∞ results were calculated without considering compound 11, as its value is not available in the result set of the Log γ_∞ calculations.

Fig. 5. Physicochemical parameters showing statistically significant Spearman's rank correlation coefficients with k at 21°C (hollow symbol) and 50°C (filled symbol). Results for all compounds 1–14 are depicted with black circles and 1–12 with red squares. The x-axis displays the physicochemical parameters, while the y-axis shows the corresponding Spearman's r values.

predictor [51]. Based on the comparison of the results with these predictors, XlogP3 demonstrated the best consideration of the *o*-, *m*- and *p*-benzyl substitution patterns and was therefore selected for assessing the Log P property.

Log P appears to serve as a valid indicator for the differences in the adsorption strength for compounds 5–14, which are expected to involve adsorption mediated by hydrogen bonding. However, compounds 1–4, that exhibit strong π -interaction effects, show weaker correlation with Log P. See Table 2. for the corresponding property values.

4.3.3. Polar surface area, hydrogen bond donor and acceptor count, and surface tension

For compounds 5–14 increasing polar surface area, water solubility, hydrogen bond donor and acceptor count, or surface tension are all associated with reduced adsorption to Sephadex® G-25 mirroring the trend observed with Log P. This reduction in adsorption is attributed to the influence of these properties on hydrogen bonding. In contrast, π -interactions with compounds 1–4 appear to be largely independent of these physicochemical parameters. See Table 2. for the corresponding property values.

4.3.4. Water solubility, and molar volume

Higher water solubility values [50] are understood to impact the adsorption strength in a way similar to lower Log P values (*vide supra*). However, the high variability of Log S (mol/L) solubility values limits the utility of this property compared to Log P values. Calculated values

[51] for molar volume [59] were not significant indicators of adsorption strength in the test series. Based on low molar volume, pore size -related effects are not expected to affect adsorption [60]. See Table 2. for the corresponding property values.

4.3.5. Activity coefficients at infinite dilution in water

For the aromatic compounds in the test series, lower Log γ_∞ is generally associated with stronger adsorption. However, the magnitude of differences with Log γ_∞ values is not proportional with the measured magnitudes of differences in the strength of adsorption. Therefore, it appears that Log γ_∞ values can be used only to compare the strength of adsorption in between closely similar substances, *i.e.* in this study within two groups of substances 1–4 and 5–12. The prerequisite for comparison is that there is distinct structural similarity between compounds. We did not study further the requirements for structural similarity.

4.4. Impact of structural properties on Adsorptivity

Based on the earlier discussion, we can conclude that physicochemical parameters are not sufficient to fully explain variations with the observed k values.

There are well studied effects that affect the reactivity of the carbon atoms in the aromatic ring, especially towards electrophilic aromatic substitution reactions. These are considered in the classic Hammett equation by using substituent parameters. Hammett parameters -based approach was also a basis for some early approaches to calculate the

differences in adsorption strength. This is taken up within the Review of Previous Research -section. In this study, this topic is touched only from the perspective of experimentally determined differences in the adsorption of differently substituted benzene rings of the compounds in the test series that was used for this study. Aromatic reactivity effects caused by the substituents is a vastly studied subject, and the phenomenon can be complex [61–64].

Substituents on an aromatic ring influence its reactivity by altering the π -electron cloud. For example, hydroxyl group (-OH) substituent exerts a +R, resonance electron-donating, effect to the π -electron cloud as its lone pair of electrons from oxygen delocalize into the ring. This increases electron density at the *o*-positions C-2 and C-6 and *p*-position C-4. Hydroxymethyl (-CH₂OH) group is also +R electron-donating, but instead of direct resonance, this occurs primarily through weak hyperconjugation. Electron withdrawing groups with -R effects, such as esters or carboxylic acids, reduce electron density at *o*- and *p*-positions, making the *m*-positions (C-3, C-5) relatively electron-rich. Therefore, acetyl group in acetophenone **3** [63] can be expected to increase electron density at *m*-position with -R effect. However, this effect is much weaker than +R induced *o*- and *p*-effects of strong donors like -OH. The conjugated carbonyl group in acetophenone extends the aromatic π -system, which is relevant for the adsorption via π -interaction.

Compounds **1-4** include benzene and its mono-substituted derivatives. In these simpler molecules, substitution effects can strengthen the nucleophilic nature of the carbons in the benzene ring. When compared with the smallest observed adsorption with benzene **2**, *k* increases in the order benzene < acetophenone < anisole < phenol. However, hydrogen bonding impacts also adsorption.

Oxygen in -OR and -OH groups withdraw electron density from the ring through the sigma bond -I inductive effect. This creates an additional reactivity weakening inductive effect.

In addition to π -interaction impacting effects, hydroxyl groups can act as hydrogen bond donors with cross-linked dextran, and the oxygen atoms, e.g. in -OCH₃ and -COCH₃ substituents, can act as hydrogen bond acceptors.

Both hydroxyl group and methoxy group in methoxyphenols **5-7** synergistically strengthen the nucleophilic nature of the free *o*- and *p*-carbons in the benzene ring due to resonance effects. For example, 3-methoxyphenol **6** exhibits the strongest adsorption, as its -OH (C-1) and -OCH₃ (C-3) groups activate C-2, C-4, and C-6, leaving three highly nucleophilic, unsubstituted carbons. In contrast, 4-methoxyphenol **5** and 2-methoxyphenol **7** have fewer activated, unsubstituted, carbon positions for the *o*- or *p*- effects of the substituents. Based on these directive effects, **5** and **7** should have similar strength of the substituent effects. However, **4** has a higher experimental *k* than **7**. Steric effects or hydrogen bonding may also affect the substitution effect in the π -system. With **7**, this effect is likely diminished by internal hydrogen bonding in between OH- and OCH₃- groups that are in vicinal *o*-position. The impact of the ortho-position impacts also physicochemical properties [8]. The boiling point of 2-methoxyphenol **7**, 205°C [64], is lower than boiling points for 3- and 4-methoxyphenols **6** and **5**, 244°C [65] and 253°C [64].

Alkyl groups, such as -CH₃, induce +I electron donating effect towards the aromatic ring affecting *o*- and *p*-positions due to hyperconjugation. -CH₂OH group in salicin **12** has also a weak net electron-donating effect via hyperconjugation from the -CH₂ group, though this is partially offset by the -I effect of the oxygen atom.

It is conceivable that there is a specific π -interaction cleft or binding pocket in Sephadex® G25 for the adsorption of benzene derivatives. This is supported by the observed linear adsorption behavior. This site likely exhibits stronger adsorption affinity for smaller aromatic molecules when a greater number of electronegative, interaction-capable positions on the aromatic ring remain unsubstituted. This concept of a locally induced π -interaction is illustrated in Fig 6.

An incremental calculation model was created in this study to demonstrate the impact of different R- and I-, and steric structure effects,

Fig. 6. Principle of the OH- and OCH₃- induced *o*- and *p*-promoting π -interaction of 3-methoxyphenol. R-OH represents an available hydroxyl group from the Sephadex® matrix.

together with the impact of temperature. In this model, the *o*- and *p*-directing +R resonance effects were summed up only to unsubstituted carbons of the benzene ring, as illustrated in Fig. 6. -R effects were considered to generally, and less significantly, weaken the π -interaction, rather than affecting specific positions, and thus were excluded from the model.

-CH₂-O-Glc (glucose) substituent was treated as a strong adsorption reducing group due to a combination of its -I character and steric shielding. Shielding effect likely reduces π -interaction also with compounds **9** and **12**, both of which feature a HOCH₂- group at *m*-position. These compounds exhibited lower-than-expected *k* values based on the expected *o*- and *p*-directed effects. This was accounted in the model with a specific *m*-effect parameter. Acetyl group in **4** increases adsorption in this model through the extension of π -system, even though it is electron withdrawing. Hydroxyl groups in benzene are generally associated with -I effects. In this model, these effects were considered minor compared to other effects, and they were therefore omitted.

Incremental calculation model based on the significant structure effects is presented in Table 4 and the results are shown also graphically in Fig. 7. The model uses the experimental retention factor of benzene as a reference and predicts the *k* values of the aromatic compounds based on their substituents. The adjustable parameters of the model, referred to as structure effect coefficients, were fitted by using the experimentally determined *k* values in three temperatures. A linear temperature dependency was assumed for a few parameters only to avoid overfitting; these temperature-dependent coefficients for 21°C are shown at the bottom of Table 4. Ridge regularization with $\lambda = 0.01$ was employed during parameter estimation to favor smaller coefficients. The *k* value of benzene **2** was set to its measured value 1.75. Some effects are overlapping in the table. Therefore, effects for different functionalities should be interpreted in a combined manner.

In Table 4, structure effects are listed on top and the structure effect coefficients and the temperature dependent coefficients are shown at the bottom. On each row, all structure effects per compound are summed up to calculate the sum of structure effects which is the predicted *k*, and comparable to experimental *k* values. The results are shown on the right.

In this calculation example, the average impact of -OCH₃ group to *k* value was +0.21 units for *k* at 21°C and +0.03 at 50°C, and between different molecules, the impact of increasing temperature to 50°C varies between -58% and -81%. For an aromatic -OH group the average impact is +0.05 units at 21°C and +0.02 at 50°C, and in between different molecules the impact of temperature increase varies between -20% and -52%. For -CH₂OH groups, the maximum impact is -0.05 units at 21°C and -0.04 at 50°C. Extension of π -system in **3** impacts *k* with +0.14 units at 21°C and +0.11 at 50°C, with -10% change. -CH₂-O-Glc (glucose) system, in **11** and **12**, was expected to affect their *k* value with -0.40 units in all temperatures. Spearman's *r* for the experimental and predicted *k* values was 0.99 (*p* value 4.18E-09) at 21°C, 0.95 (*p* value 0.05) at 35°C and 0.98 (*p* value 6.75E-08) at 50°C.

Table 4

Sum of structure effects is used to predict k . Temperature dependencies are linear: $y(T) = y(T_{ref}) + a(T - T_{ref})$ with $T_{ref} = 21^\circ\text{C}$.

compound's structural features	π ring system benzene	+R o- and p-OH	+R o- and p-OCH ₃	extension of π -system to (carbonyl group) COCH ₃	+I CH ₂ OH (alkyls in general)	observed meta-effect CH ₂ OH	+R (m-directing) OH	+R (m-directing) OCH ₃	-I OCH ₃ excluding OH	-O...H-bond donor OH	-I, steric effect CH ₂ -O-Glc	predicted k			experimental k		
												21 °C	35 °C	50 °C	21°C	35°C	50°C
1 OCH ₃	1		3					2	1			2.03		1.92	1.99	1.95	
2 none	1											1.75		1.75	1.75	1.76	
3 COCH ₃	1			1								1.91	1.89	1.86	1.92	1.89	1.86
4 OH	1	3					2					2.12		1.97	2.09	2.01	
5 OH, p-OCH ₃	1	2	2				2			1		2.21	2.13	2.05	2.29	2.17	2.06
6 OH, m-OCH ₃	1	3	3				1	1	1	1		2.46	2.34	2.21	2.48	2.33	2.20
7 OH, o-OCH ₃	1	2	2				2	2	1	1		2.21	2.13	2.05	2.17	2.09	2.00
8 OH, o-CH ₂ OH	1	2			1					2		1.95		1.84	1.99	1.86	
9 OH, m-CH ₂ OH	1	3			1	1				2		1.99		1.84	1.97	1.85	
10 OH, p-CH ₂ OH	1	2			1					2		1.95		1.84	1.93	1.81	
11 CH ₂ -O-Glc (glucose)	1									4	1	1.29		1.29	1.27	1.29	
12 O-Glc, m-CH ₂ OH	1				1	1				5	1	1.31		1.30	1.31	1.30	
Structure effect coefficients (a)	1.750	0.282	-0.319	-0.399	0.260	-0.035	0.073	-0.137	0.246	-0.015	-0.402						
$y(21^\circ\text{C})$		(-5.99E-03)	(3.81E-03)	(4.03E-03)	(-8.13E-04)												
		0.281	-0.319	-0.399	0.260												

Fig. 7. The results based on Table 4 are shown in graph format. Open symbols: experimental values; filled symbols: predicted values.

In the studied set of compounds, temperature did not significantly affect the underlying π -interaction. However, it impacted significantly adsorption through hydrogen bonding-related effects. The temperature effect on the adsorption was less pronounced for 2-methoxyphenol 7 compared to 4-methoxyphenol 5 and 3-methoxyphenol 6. This suggests that a strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding between vicinal substituents on the aromatic ring can reduce the sensitivity of the adsorption to temperature change (see Table 2 and Fig 4).

In addition to small aromatic compounds, the k values for two free sugars were also measured for comparison. Glucose 13 and cellobiose 14, exhibited the lowest k values, indicating only weak interaction with Sephadex® G-25. For these compounds, adsorption was only minimally influenced by temperature. The slight differences observed between sugars may be attributed primarily to differences in molecular size. Slightly less adsorbing cellobiose 14 may be more affected by steric hindrance when attempting to access optimal sites on the Sephadex surface or within its pores. In addition, its larger size and reduced conformational flexibility may limit its ability to adopt energetically favorable binding orientations. As a general principle, when adsorption involves combined weak molecular interactions like several hydroxyl- or CH₂-groups, or more than one saccharide unit, these effects may act

cooperatively, resulting in an overall interaction that is stronger than the sum of the individual contributions. Such cooperative effects may also be associated with specific binding interactions on the surface of cross-linked dextran gel. However, since only two free sugars were included in this test series, no definitive conclusions on these interactions can be drawn.

A similar structure-based explanation (see Table 4), can be useful for interpreting the order and relative strength of adsorption among other aromatic compounds. When examining the earlier reported K_D values from aqueous Sephadex G-25® chromatography at room temperature, differences in adsorption strength can be attributed to substitution-pattern-related effects for phenol, 1,4-dihydroxybenzene, 1,3-dihydroxybenzene, 3-methylphenol, and 4-methylphenol [28] as well as for phenol, 1,4-dihydroxybenzene, 1,3-dihydroxybenzene, 1,3,5-trihydroxybenzene, 1,2-dihydroxybenzene and 1,2,3-trihydroxybenzene [2]. To fully account for π -interaction effects in these compounds, it is necessary to introduce a +I parameter for aromatic ring methylation, along with an additional +R resonance contribution for *ortho*-position effects, specifically for the 1,2-OH and 1,2,3-OH *ortho*-hydroxyl-interactions [26,2].

Aromatic substitution pattern effects also explain why triandrin elutes significantly later than salicin and picein in aqueous Sephadex® G-10 chromatography, but exhibits the same retention time when a weak cation exchange resin (CA10GC in Na⁺ form) is used [6]. In addition to +R effects from its -OH group, triandrin contains an alkene linkage to the aromatic ring, which contributes +I inductive and, hyperconjugative effects. These enhance the π -interaction of triandrin with Sephadex® G-10 gel. Thus, triandrin possesses two structural features that promote π -interaction, whereas picein and salicin only have one. Conversely, in ion exchange chromatography π -interactions are not a dominant adsorption mechanism, so differences in aromatic substitution are not expected to significantly affect elution order. In the same study, the notably weak adsorption of (+)-catechin to Sephadex® G-10, is also likely due to structural factors. Steric hindrance from its bulky framework may limit effective π -interaction with the gel matrix.

The combined strength of structure effects can be temperature-dependent, as shown in Table 4 and Fig. 7. Non-chemical adsorption is typically exothermic, meaning that an increase in temperature generally reduces adsorption capacity. Additionally, higher temperatures accelerate the rate of sorption processes [66]. These effects explain

the general trend of shorter retention times at elevated temperatures. However, temperature increase does not always lead to a consistent reduction in retention time; in some cases, even peak reversals may occur [67]. In this study, k was generally lower at higher temperature. Nevertheless, small positive changes in k were observed for compounds 2, 11 and 12. As an additional feature, the presence of distinct temperature zones with differing water geometries in the gel, that have been previously reported for Sephadex® G-10 [23], may contribute to non-linear thermodynamic behavior in adsorption.

4.5. Thermodynamic parameters

Van't Hoff plot, shown in Fig. 8, presents the observed temperature-dependent retention factor differences. The data for the plot were derived from the differences in k values for all compounds from the experiments at 21°C (20 ± 3°C) and at 50°C, and additionally at 35°C for compounds 3, 5, 6 and 7. The slope and intercept of the plot were used to calculate enthalpy, entropy and the change in Gibbs free energy at 20°C based on Equations (5) and (7). The results are presented in Table 2. Comparisons of ΔH and ΔS values for the compounds in the test series are shown in Fig. 9.

We can anticipate that similar compounds have similar values for enthalpy changes, as described in Eq. (9), indicated by the slope $-\Delta H^\circ/R$. The enthalpy change reflects the temperature dependence of the binding constant. However, it is generally unclear how many or which specific equilibria contribute to the observed thermodynamic behavior [68]. Variations with entropy changes may be more directly associated with different interaction mechanisms. This is reflected in the intercept values, which correspond to $\Delta S^\circ/R$. Such interpretation have been applied in earlier studies involving benzoates [8], as well as alcohols and halogenated phenols in Sephadex® G-25 chromatography [36]. To further explore potential differences in adsorption mechanisms, enthalpy-entropy compensation plot was constructed based on Eq. (5), using data collected at 21°C and 50°C, see Fig. 9.

In the enthalpy-entropy compensation plot, compounds with similar adsorption interaction mechanism are expected to cluster together or align along linear trends. In addition, the plot reveals how much the temperature difference influences these mechanisms. Based on visual inspection, compounds 1-10 (where π -interaction dominates) and 11-14

Fig. 8. Van't Hoff plot of $\ln k$ versus temperature $10^3/T$. Trendlines for compounds 3, 5, 6 and 7 are based on three retention time measurements (21°C, 35°C and 50°C) while the remaining trendlines are based on two measurements (21°C and 50°C). The x-axis represents $10^3/T$ and y-axis $\ln K$.

Fig. 9. Enthalpy-entropy compensation plot shows the adsorption enthalpy (ΔH° , x-axis) versus entropy contribution ($-T \cdot \Delta S^\circ$, y-axis) at 21 °C (open circles) and at 50 °C (closed circles). Values are derived from Gibbs free energy (ΔG) calculations based on the retention factor k for compounds 1-14 in the test series (see Table 2).

(where glucose moieties participate) appear to form two broader groups. More specific subgroupings are also possible. For example, the following clusters may be identified: compounds a) 1-4, b) 5-7, c) 8-10, d) 11-12, e) 11, 13 and 14, and possibly f) 2 and 12.

Therefore, it is possible to distinguish five to seven different combinations of adsorption mechanisms among the compounds. These groupings align with the earlier discussion (*vide supra*) regarding the influence of various hydrogen bonding effects and π -interaction on the retention factor k . Glucosylated compounds 11-14 cluster closely together.

Earlier suggestion [37], that ΔH reflects the strength of interaction between the compounds and Sephadex® gel, appears consistent when comparing similar types of compounds and their k values, particularly compounds 1-10. For these compounds, a higher k value is also associated with more negative ΔS values. This trend, however, is not observed for the glucosidated compounds 11-14. This supports the understanding that glucosylated compounds interact with the gel through a different adsorption mechanism compared to non-glucosylated compounds. The variation in ΔS may also reflect changes in the freedom of molecular motion during adsorption, which could also contribute to this deviation.

An additional example of interaction with Sephadex® G-25 has been reported for tryptophan [69]. Its adsorption is expected to be stronger than that observed for the compounds in our test series. Reported values include $K_d = 2.64$ at 25°C, $\Delta H = -1.57$ kJ/mol, $\Delta S = -3.30$ J/(mol K) and $\Delta G = -0.59$ kJ/mol. Based on enthalpy-entropy characteristics, tryptophan aligns closely with the linear trends observed for compounds 1-11, particularly with the cluster formed by compounds 8-10. This suggests that tryptophan may share similar interaction mechanisms with the gel.

4.6. Conclusions

The adsorption interactions of small aromatic compounds in aqueous Sephadex® G-25 gel chromatography are influenced by the compound's physicochemical and structural properties, as well as by temperature.

When comparing physicochemical properties using Spearman's rank correlation with the strength of adsorption of the compounds in the test series, it was observed that lower values for topological polar surface area, and sum of hydrogen bond donors, were significant indicators of stronger adsorption. These properties can be associated with hydrogen bond mediated adsorption. Additionally, a higher octanol-water partition coefficient and lower values for surface tension, and the activity coefficient in infinite dilution in water also correlated with stronger adsorption. These properties can be associated with a preference for the

adsorbent phase when water is used as the eluent.

In conclusion, physicochemical parameters can serve as useful indicators of the expected differences in the strength of adsorption for small aromatic compounds. However, physicochemical data alone is not sufficient to accurately predict the retention order or relative adsorption strength.

Based on the measured retention factors, it is possible to distinguish simultaneously acting π -interaction mechanisms and hydrogen bonding-mediated effects as the main contributors to the adsorption. Among these, π -interaction had the stronger impact to adsorption in the test series. Its strength is related to the substitution pattern of the compound, which induces either electron-donating, or electron-withdrawing, effects on the free carbon atoms of the aromatic ring, thereby modulating the strength of π -interaction.

It is expected that the site of π -interaction is associated with the glyceryl ether linkage in epichlorohydrin cross-linked dextran gel. The chemical structure of the solute, particularly in close proximity to its π -system, can further enhance the adsorption via hydrogen bonding. Intermolecular effects, especially shielding effects affecting π -interaction, may also impact adsorption strength. We propose that such a shielding effect, which reduces adsorption strength, was observed for the $-CH_2OH$ substituent in the *meta*-position in compounds 3-hydroxybenzyl alcohol, and salicin.

Hydrogen bonding-mediated adsorption is primarily associated with hydroxyl groups, but methoxy ($-OCH_3$) and acetyl groups can also contribute to this type of adsorption. Hydrogen bonding is significantly influenced by temperature. In the test series, the strongest temperature-dependent effects were observed in compounds containing two hydrogen bonding-related substituents on the same benzene ring. As a result, 2-, 3- and 4-methoxyphenols as well as 2-, 3- and 4-hydroxybenzyl alcohols, exhibited significantly stronger adsorption at 21°C compared to 50°C.

These conclusions are supported by the enthalpy-entropy compensation plot for adsorption. It shows that the small aromatic compounds exhibiting similar types of adsorption mechanisms align along a common trendline, with stronger adsorption associated with lower ΔH and ΔS values. In contrast, glucosylated aromatic compounds do not follow the same trajectory, suggesting a different adsorption mechanism.

Structural information of the small aromatic compounds is used in this study to demonstrate that the retention factor k can be calculated based on the sum of structure effects, originating from the cumulative effects of their substitution patterns. Resonance, inductive and hydrogen bonding-related effects, along with temperature correlations for the hydrogen bonding strength, are used in an incremental prediction model to obtain similar k values as the observed ones. This structure-based approach serves as a useful tool for estimating relative adsorption strengths and predicting the expected retention order of small aromatic compounds.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Reko L. Lehtilä: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tuomo Sainio:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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